

A Study of Relationship of Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievements of Students Studying at Senior Secondary Level

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Received : 09/02/2023

1st BPR : 15/02/2023

2nd BPR : 23/02/2023

Accepted : 02/03/2023

Abstract

The present study is conducted with the objective to measure the relationship of Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement of senior secondary level students. This is a survey study under descriptive research. For the this study, 100 students were selected randomly as the samples of J.V. Jain Inter College, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh. For the collection of data the researcher administrated the Smartphone Addiction Scale by Vijayshri and Dr. Masaud Ansari, and for Academic Achievement, the scores of class 10th of such students were considered. After that, data of Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement scores were calculated and relationship between them was sought with Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and the results were analyzed & interpretations were drawn. The levels of significance were kept 0.01 and 0.05 to test the hypotheses. It was observed from the findings of the variables that there is no significant relationship exists between them.

Keywords: Smartphone, Addiction, Academic Achievement, Senior Secondary.

Introduction :

Smartphone has made students' lives easier, as they can access their school information on the gadget through electronic learning (e-learning), and mobile learning (m learning) as well as they can learn or get any kind of knowledge on them. Despite so many advantages & benefits of smartphones on students, there are so many disadvantages and negative impacts as well, which cannot be neglected. There are still some questions that call for attention when it comes to students using smartphones in their academic journey. The questions involve, do students benefit from using smartphones academically? Is it helping to improve students' Academic performance? The more students use smartphone, the More they are exposed to many positive and negative impacts. Smartphone Addiction is a disorder involving compulsive overuse of the mobile devices, usually quantified as the number of times user access their devices or the total amount of time they are online over a specified period.

Academic Achievement is the resultant outcomes that shows the extent to which a student has achieved his learning objectives. Academic Achievement is often measured through examinations or continuous assessments.

Literature Review :

Mehrotra & Nehra (2022), investigated the "Impact of Smartphone Addiction on Academic Performance of Adolescents in Rajasthan". The findings suggested two important aspects to understand the impact of smartphone addiction on academic performance of adolescents. The negative impact their learning and academic performance, while the positive aspect indicates that the use of smartphone by adolescents increase their skills and cognitive abilities, thereby improving their

academic performance. Rathakrishnan et. al. (2021), investigated in their study that the greater the smartphone addiction was found to be associated with lower the academic performance. Kaur(2018), conducted a study & the findings suggested that Mobile Phone usage effect the academic performance of the students as they stuck to this device during their classes. Nayak (2018), investigated that women are more involved in using smart phone than males but on the other hand the adverse effect of using smart phone are on males. Chaudhary & Tripathy (2018), found that smartpone usage had a negative impact on academic performance.

Significance of the study : This study provided an insight to the recognized reliance on the use of smartphone in this day & age. The findings of the study are beneficial because most of the individuals do not realize how much smartphone addiction hinders their academic achievement, even in the minor way. This study enhances the understanding on the relationship of smartphone addiction and academic achievement of students.

Statement of Problem: “A study of Relationship of Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement of Students Studying at Senior Secondary Level”.

Delimitation of the study:

- 1- The present study has been limited to the students at studying senior of Uttar Pradesh Board of Education.
- 2- The present study has not been reached to the every age group that use smartphone.
- 3- This study has been confined to students of J.V. Jain Inter, College, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

Objectives :

- 1- To study the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement of student studying at senior secondary level.
- 2- To Study the relationship between Compulsion and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 3- To study the relationship between Forgetfulness and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 4- To study the relationship between Lack of Attention and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 5- To study the relationship between Depression/ Anxiety and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 6- To study the relationship between Disturbed hunger/ sleep and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 7- To study the relationship between Social Withdrawal and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.

Hypotheses :

- 1- There is no significant relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement of is students studying at senior secondary level.
- 2- There is no significant relationship between Compulsion and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 3- There is no significant relationship between Forgetfulness and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 4- There is no significant relationship between Lack of Attention and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 5- There is no significant relationship between Depression/ Anxiety and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 6- There is no significant relationship between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.

- 7- There is no significant relationship between Social Withdrawal and Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level.

Methodology :

- ❖ **Research Design-** The Descriptive Survey Research Method has been applied in the study.
- ❖ **Population, Sample, Age Limit of Sample-** The present study consisted 100 students (50 males & 50 females) of senior secondary level of J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India, of age group 15 to 19 years old.
- ❖ **Variables-**
 - Independent Variables - Smartphone Addiction
 - Dependent Variables - Academic Achievement
- ❖ **Tools-** To measure Smartphone Addiction, Smartphone Addiction Scale constructed by Dr. Vijayshri & Dr. Masaud Ansari has been used. This tool has six dimensions namely Compulsion, Forgetfulness, Lack of Attention, Depression/ Anxiety, Distributed Hunger/ Sleep and Social Withdrawal.
To measure Academic Achievement, class 10th scores of students has been considered.
- ❖ **Statistical Techniques-** Product Moment Correlation has been used to measure the relationship between of both the variables, Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement.

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

To test the relationship between the variables of the study Pearson's Product Moment correlation technique was applied. Significance of correlation coefficient was checked afterwards to test the significance of the hypotheses.

The results obtained are mentioned in the given table:

S.No.	Relationship Between	'r' value	Level of significance
1	Smartphone Addiction & Academic Achievement	-0.060	Not Significant
2	Compulsion & Academic Achievement	-0.17	Not Significant
3	Forgetfulness & Academic Achievement	0.087	Not Significant
4	Lack of Attention & Academic Achievement	0.039	Not Significant
5	Depression/Anxiety & Academic Achievement	0.0213	Not Significant
6	Distributed Hunger/Sleep & Academic Achievement	-0.293	Not Significant
7	Social Withdrawal & Academic Achievement	0.0561	Not Significant

Interpretation for Hypothesis 1: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0.060. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Smartphone Addiction & Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 2: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0.17. Thus there is negative but low relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Compulsion & Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 3: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.087. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship

exist between Forgetfulness & Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 4: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.039. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Lack of Attention & Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 5: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.0213. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Depression/Anxiety & Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 6: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0.293. Thus there is negative but low level of relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Distributed Hunger/Sleep & Academic Achievement of students studying at Senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 7: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.00561. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Social Withdrawal & Academic Achievement of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion:

This study finds the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Academic Achievement based upon the correlation coefficients presented through the table. On the basis of findings of the study it may be concluded that the Smartphone Addiction along with its dimensions has negative correlation with Academic Achievement, although the magnitude of relationship is very low or almost negligible. The findings are in support of the notion that there is high level of smartphone addiction leads low academic achievement.

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